

Principal Mathematical Model for Material Fracture Mechanics

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The equation of a real-structure material's elastic-plastic fracture has been developed using the energy conservation law and without the need for linear fracture mechanics (LFM) postulates. This equation has been used to determine the force and energy criterion of Non-linear Fracture Mechanics (NLFM). Modern strength analyses of machine components and structures composed of real-structure materials are based on these criteria. For several steels, the experimental confirmation of the K_{1c} dependency on impact toughness, yield limit, and ultimate strength limit has been demonstrated.

Elastic Fracture Mechanics (EFA) is regarded as the foundation for contemporary strength analysis of load-bearing structures and components. The force criterion (K_{1c}) and the energy criterion (G_{1c}) of material fracture, represented by Equation (1) and Equation (2) respectively, are recognized as the fundamental equations of EFA. These criteria are expressed as follows:

$$K_{1c} = c\sigma\sqrt{\pi l} \quad (1)$$

$$G_{1c} = K_{1c}^2/E \quad (2)$$

Where K_{1c} represents the Critical Stress Intensity Factor (CSIF) or crack resistance (CR), σ denotes the ultimate stress limit of a specimen containing a crack of length l is a factor dependent on the specimen's geometry and testing conditions, G_{1c} signifies crack toughness, and E is the normal modulus of elasticity.

The aforementioned fracture criteria were derived based on the following assumptions:

1. It is assumed that the broken material is elastic, which means that the applied stress immediately affects its relative strain. Elastic Fracture Mechanics (EFM) is the term used to describe the fracture mechanics that were developed based on this assumption.
2. As opposed to discrete, or atomic, structure, the material structure extends.
3. The crack's corner stress σ_y is ∞ and its tip radius (ρ) is 0.

Its force and energy EFM criterion may be derived from the physical model of fracturing, which is based on the aforementioned assumptions. However, this model is rather far from actual operating and research circumstances for the components composed of these materials (and their fracture patterns).

Furthermore, the dimension of K_{1c} does not accurately reflect its considerable content when compared to the dimensions of other structural and tool material qualities. One well-known expert in the field of fracture mechanics said that the physical sense of parameter K is difficult to understand mostly due to its dimension, which is rather hard to physically imagine.

Let us examine a plate of a material that is not necessarily elastic and has a thickness of δ . The drawing plane does not constrain the plate's size, and the stress σ affects the plate. Assume that a thorough fracture developed in a specific region of the plate as a result of a stress. $\sigma_y > \sigma$.

While stress σ applied to the plate is the mediating factor of the crack, stress σ_y forming in its corners is the direct cause of the $2l$ -long fracture's formation. It is clear that the fracture energy W_y and W of forces P_y and P , which explain why stresses σ_y and σ occur once, are equal. Let's calculate and equalize these energy' values:

$$W_y = P_y \times S_y \quad (3)$$

P_y is the fracturing force, while S_y is the transfer (broadening) of a crack toward P_y . As for it:

$$P_y = (\sigma_y - \sigma) \times \delta \times \Delta \quad (4)$$

where $(\sigma_y - \sigma)$ is the plate's ultimate stress that is impacted by the action of stress σ prior to the onset of σ_y stress (in fact, if $\sigma_y = \sigma$ fracture force $P_y = 0$, the plate is undisturbed by definition, but under the action of stress σ); -the smallest unretrievable displacement of the fracture edges that appears at the tip when the ultimate force is applied. The value Δ is clearly equal to the interatomic spacer b in a material with a true discrete structure. As a result, the displacement energy of the crack opening is:

$$W_y = \frac{1}{2}(\sigma_y - \sigma) \times \delta \times \Delta \times 2a \quad (5)$$

The displacement of crack S_y in the direction of force P_y during crack extension up to length $2l$ is represented by the cofactor $2a$ (crack opening); the crack opening value $2a$ is the sum of irretrievable displacements Δ of both crack edges occurring at its tip ($2a = \sum \Delta$); the cofactor $\frac{1}{2}$ accounts for the fact that the ultimate stress varies from 0 to $(\sigma_y - \sigma)$. To form the two fracture faces, force P must exert the following work:

$$W = \sigma \times 2l \times \delta \times \Delta \quad (6)$$

Once equations (5) and (6) are equivalent, we get:

$$\frac{1}{2}(\sigma_y - \sigma) \times 2a = 2\sigma l \quad (7)$$

The desired equation may be obtained from equation (7):

$$\sigma_y = \sigma \left(l + \frac{2l}{a} \right) \quad (8)$$

According to equation (8), we get the following for a plate with a circular hole of radius r ($r = l = a$):

$$\sigma_y = 3\sigma \quad (9)$$

Using equation (6) and its condition $\rho = \frac{a^2}{l}$, we may derive the following if the fracture is thought to have an elliptical form:

$$\sigma_y = \sigma(1 + 2\sqrt{l/\rho}) \quad (10)$$

It has been established that this equation holds for every type of fracture where a point with a tiny curvature radius ρ is located on its periphery. Given that $2\sqrt{l/\rho} \gg 1$, we may express (8) as follows:

$$\sigma_y = 2\sigma\sqrt{l/\rho} \quad (11)$$

For a lateral fracture with length l and curvature radius ρ , this equation also holds. Let's take (11) and multiply both portions by $\sqrt{p}$:

$$\sigma_y \sqrt{p} = 2\sigma \sqrt{l} \quad (12)$$

When a plate fractures with an edge crack of length l , the right-hand portion of equation (12) can be converted into the fracture mechanics force criteria K_{1c} .

$$\sigma_y \sqrt{p} = K_{1c} = 2\sigma \sqrt{l} = 1.13\sigma \sqrt{\pi l} \quad (13)$$

In the equation above the exterior stresses are represented by $\sigma = \sigma_B$ – ultimate stress limit, whereas the interior stresses are represented by $\sigma_y - \sigma$. Equations (8) through (11) are widely recognized. A.Griffiths obtained them, and the right-hand part of equation type (13) can be found in J. Irvin's research for the case of material fracturing with the aforementioned assumptions 1-3 taken into account, i.e., for the elastic continuum of an ideal structure having a crack with $\rho \rightarrow 0$ and $\sigma_y \rightarrow \infty$. Without using the EFA postulate, let's demonstrate that the primary equation (5) and the following equation (13) about the linear dependency of relative material deformation on applied stress are derived from the energy conservation law.

Let's construct equation (7) for a plate with a lateral fracture of length l which shows the ultimate stress $\sigma_y - \sigma$.

$$(\sigma_y - \sigma) \times a = 2\sigma l \quad (14)$$

By diverging the faces of one of the crack tips, as opposed to the two crack tips diverging as occurs in the case of a central crack, the lateral crack opening, in this case, is equal to $\Sigma\Delta$ and is twice as tiny as the central crack. According to fracture toughness G_{1c} , the energy required to produce a unit fracture surface area during crack extension is represented by the left-hand portion of equation (12). J. Rise's J_{1c} -integral, which was derived using the energy conservation rule as an energy criterion of elastic-plastic material fracture (nonlinear fracture mechanics criterion), likewise has a comparable physical significance and dimension.

$$J_{1c} = \sigma_0 \times \delta_k \quad (15)$$

where σ_0 is the breaking stress at the tip of a lateral crack and δ_k is the opening of a lateral crack ($\delta_k = a$). In addition, the multiplicands of the right-hand portion of equation (15) σ and l clearly establish the value $1.13\sigma \sqrt{\pi l} = 2\sigma \sqrt{l(11)}$. The energy criteria for nonlinear fracture mechanics of a real-structure material (NEFM) may be derived using a few straightforward basic expressions:

$$G_{1c} = J_{1c} = \frac{(K_{1c})^2}{2\sigma_B} \quad (16)$$

$$K_{1c}(CB) = \sqrt{2\sigma_B} \times G_{1c}(J_{1c}) \quad (17)$$

The fact that equations (7) and (13) were produced in this study without the use of Hooke Law should also be noted.

During the fracture process, the assumption that the radius of a crack tip curving in a plate made of a real-structure material with discrete structure $\rho \rightarrow 0$ and the stress in its tip $\sigma_y \rightarrow \infty$ can be excluded by using the crack model. In reality, ρ in such a material cannot be less than interatomic space b , and σ_y cannot be more than the theoretical upper limit σ_{theor} . This finding led to the

observation that the material with a blunt crack had a much higher cracking resistance (by 13%) than that with a sharp break: $1.13\sigma\sqrt{\pi l}$ (equation (13) and $\sigma\sqrt{\pi l}$ respectively.

It is obvious that the numbers K_{1c} given in reference material often relate to fractures with $\rho \rightarrow 0$. The universal, two-fold character of the force fracture criterion K_{1c} is reflected in equation (11). In its left-hand part the stress intensity factor in the case of brittle, that is elastic fracture K_{1c} (CSIF) is equal to $\sigma_y\sqrt{\rho}$, and the one in its right-hand side – to cracking resistance $K_{1c}(CR) = 2\sigma\sqrt{l}$ for elastic-plastic fracturing.

$K_{1c}(CSIF)$ is a force criterion of EFM in the first instance as its value is only dependent on $\sigma_y \approx 0.1E$ and $\rho \approx b$, or the characteristics of a material with perfect structure. This type of material is prone to elastic, brittle fracturing because it lacks any imperfections, especially dislocations, whose migration and creation cause material plastic deformation. In several labs, specimens composed of flawless materials have been acquired. Their final strength in the experiment, σ_B , seems to match the appropriate estimated value, $\sigma_{theort} = \psi(E, b)$. The iron-base alloys have $K_{1c}(CSIF) = 0.38$; ($E \approx 220000MPa$), the left-hand third part of (13) indicates.

With the experimental values σ and l taken into account, the value of $K_{1c}(PR)$ in steels (the iron-based alloys) computed according to the right-hand part of (15) significantly surpasses the values of $K_{1c}(CSIF)$ and amounts to 100 to 130, or 250 to 300 times as large, for the case of elastic-plastic material fracturing. E. Orovan showed experimentally that plastic fracture energy values are several orders of magnitude greater than brittle fracturing energy values, and these results support his findings.

It is necessary to distinguish between the criteria $K_{1c}(CR)$ and $K_{1c}(CSIF)$ since they do not share the same values or sense.

Concurrently, it was discovered that the criteria K_{1c} , which had derived from a fracturing model and in compliance with the presumptions (1-3) of EFM, could be applied as a criterion of elastic-plastic fracturing of a real-structure component. The allowable values of fracture lengths l_{cr} of various materials under plain-strain circumstances, were shown to properly match the pertinent experimental data. D explained this surprising outcome.

Because of the appearance of a tiny layer of plastically deformed material near the crack tip, which causes the material to change into a quasi-brittle state, the asymptotic equations EFM remain valid. This thin layer is often restricted in size, accounting for no more than 20% of the fracture length. However, the K_{1c} value is frequently and effectively used to calculate the critical crack length (l_{cr}) of many building materials, where the formation of a substantial zone of plastically deformed material occurs before the crack starts to develop.

One may owe certain materials, such as high-temper structural steels, to them is the linear dimension of the plastic deformation zone δ_p at the lateral crack tip that occurs just before its expansion under plain-strain conditions.

$$\delta_p = (1/3\pi)(K_{1c}/\sigma T)^2 \quad (18)$$

$$L_{crack} = 0.25(K_{1c}/\sigma_B)^2 \quad (19)$$

One may determine the relative size of the plastic deformation zone at the edge crack tip right before the material fracture by using equations (15) and (18).

$$\delta_p/L_{crack} = 0.42(\sigma_B/\sigma_T)^2 \quad (20)$$

One may approximate the relationship δ_p/L_{crack} using equation (19). talking about a standard structural steel grade 40X. The steel's hardness may reach 30 to 32 HRC after conventional heat treatment, and its σ_B and σ_T values are 1030 and 800 MPa, respectively. According to equation (19), 70% of the steel's overall length is made up of the plastic zone at the 40X crack tip. This experimentally measured zone is much larger than the crack length in steel.

As previously stated, this zone shouldn't be more than 20% l_{cr} , however the δ_p/l_{cr} numbers listed above significantly surpass the value of a thin layer. Therefore, the argument that the rules of EFM apply to elastic-plastic materials because they transition into a quasi-brittle state by forming a thin deformed layer at the crack tip does not seem to be strong enough. Because of this, the current situation can be directly explained by the acquired demonstration that the force fracture criteria $K_{1c}(CR)$ is a direct outcome of the energy conservation rule without being restricted by EFM postulates.

In order to support the potential of using the EFM force criteria $K_{1c}(CSIF)$ in the context of the elastic-plastic fracture of these materials, it is clear that the hypothesis of the quasi-brittle fracturing of genuine materials was proposed. The reason is really because $K_{1c}(CR)$ is a criterion of non-linear mechanics of the fracture of real-structure materials. The value G_{lc} is determined using equations or (20) and is frequently selected as the energy criteria of elastic-plastic fracture:

$$G_{1c} = J_{1c} = [K_{1c}(CR)]^2/E \quad (21)$$

There is a significant discrepancy between the values of G_{lc} derived from equations (16) and (20). Equation (16) enables the calculation of the J_{lc} –integral G_{lc} using the experimental values of σ_B and $K_{1c}(CR)$. Thus far, J_{lc} has been established by highly complex and specialized studies. Elastic-plastic and really brittle fractures are both covered by equation (16) as it was derived from the fundamental equation (7) and equation (12), which follows from it. Let's use the latter scenario to verify this assertion. Here, $K_{1c}(PR)$ should be naturally included in equation (16) in place of $K_{1c}(PSIF)$. The brittle fracture causes a new surface to form. $E[J] = \gamma \times S$, where γ is the surface energy, S is the fracture surface area, and a certain amount of energy needs to be used to generate this surface. In the solid form, iron (Fe_a) has been experimentally shown to have $\gamma = 1750$ erg/cm² (1.75 J/m²).

Given that, as previously demonstrated, the value of $K_{1c}(CSIF)$ in Fe_a is 0.38 MPam^{1/2}, and $\sigma_B = \sigma_{theory} \approx 2200MPa$, we can determine that, for iron, G_{lc} is about 3.28J/m² by inserting these values into equation (18). Two surfaces are created as a result of the fracturing process, therefore the experimental value of surface energy γ and the value of G_{lc} , which is 1.75 and 1.64 J/m², will essentially correspond.

When evaluating the accuracy of the aforementioned statement in the context of elastic-plastic fracture, it is important to keep in mind that the specific energy of fracture surface generation [J/m²] is equal to the impact toughness, such as KCU, and the fracture toughness G_{lc} . As a result, using equations (16) and (20) to compare their estimated and experimental values is possible. For example, H18K9M5T, $\sigma_B \approx 2000MPa$, $K_{1c} = 60MPa$ for maraging steel. Equations (16) and (20) show that $G_{lc} = 0.90MJ/m^2$ and $0.014MJ/m^2$, respectively. The experimental value KCU is about 0.40 MJ/m². As a result, the value of G_{lc} , which is determined by equation (16) and comes from the primary equation (7), is greater than the impact strength value. Because of its eclectic nature, equation (20) is not valid for either genuine brittle fracture or elastic-plastic fracture.

The circumstances of fracturing specimens with a fracture created at their tips and those of notched specimens intended to determine their K_{1c} or KCU is similar, and one should be aware of this since both situations lead to the creation of the plain-strain state during specimen testing. When compared to crack-resistance testing, impact testing's higher loading rate (5–10 m/sec) has only a little influence on the material's plastic qualities. A notch significantly lowers the energy of a specimen fracture, while the length of an induced crack has no effect on the value of $K_{1c}(CR)$, which is a material constant. This is the primary distinction.

$$K_{1c} = 2.38\sqrt{\sigma_B} \times KCU \quad (22)$$

As a result of the creation of a zone of plastically deformed material at the crack tip, the value K_{1c} in (21) must be raised to K_{1c} in the event of a clear elastic-plastic fracture.

$$K_{1c}(el - pl)/K_{1c}(el) = \sqrt{(l + \delta_p)}/\sqrt{l} \quad (23)$$

$$\sigma_B\sqrt{l} = \sigma_m\sqrt{(l + \delta_p)} \quad (24)$$

$$K_{1c}(el - pl)/K_{1c}(el) = \sigma_B/\sigma_T \quad (25)$$

$$K_{1c}(CT) = 2.38\sigma_B/\sigma_T(\sqrt{\sigma_B} \times KCU)MPa \quad (26)$$

It is feasible to achieve good results by applying Relationship (25) with the literature data on the values σ_B , σ_m , KCU, and $K_{1c}(CR)$ for a number of steels.

In some situations, it is not possible to compare values $(K_{1c})^{cal}$ and $(K_{1c})^{exp}$ if they differ by more than 25%.

Insufficiently accurate findings of estimating the impact strength appear to be the primary explanation behind it. It is heavily influenced by the lack of a defined method for creating impact test specimens (and, initially, creating the notches on their surfaces). A portion of the fracture energy used to calculate the impact strength is also used for the bending and tightening of elastic and plastic (residual) specimens. Determining Izod's impact toughness will likely lessen this energy loss. Additionally, it has been noted that the steels that exhibit the most significant differences between calculated and experimental values of $K_{1c}(CT)$ during specimen testing exhibit structural and property changes, such as maraging.

Presumably, the criteria $K_{1c}(CR)$ is incorrect for long or lap (crack) seams when the connection between the crack length l and opening a , which is utilized to derive equation (7), is disrupted.

$$\sigma = \frac{K_{1c}}{c\sqrt{\pi l}} \quad (27)$$

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